

DIFFUSE INFILTRATIVE ABDOMINAL LIPOMATOSIS – CASE REPORT**Dragos F. Voicu**

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Abstract

Diffuse infiltrative lipomatosis is a rare condition characterized by extensive proliferation of non-encapsulated adipose tissue, that invades local structures. It is histologically benign, similar to simple lipoma. Infiltrative lipomatosis, evolving in the abdominal cavity, including the retroperitoneal spaces, is a particular form.

Computed tomography is the imaging examination of choice, allowing determination of the location, size and extension of the lipomatous tumor and delimitation from adjacent structures. It is also useful for surgical management and assessment of the feasibility of complete resection.

A case of diffuse infiltrative lipomatosis, involving the peritoneal cavity and retroperitoneal space, which was resolved surgically is presented.

Keywords: abdominal lipomatosis, computed tomography, surgery

Introduction

Diffuse infiltrative lipomatosis is a rare condition characterized by extensive proliferation and excessive growth of non-encapsulated adipose tissue, with infiltration of surrounding tissues [1]. The histological structure is benign, similar to that of simple lipomas, but the invasive nature of this lesion has a lethal potential. In most cases (80%), the lesion develops distally, but it can affect practically any anatomical region (face, head and neck, trunk, abdominal cavity, pelvis). Involvement of the abdomino-pelvic cavity, including the retroperitoneal spaces, by diffuse infiltrative lipomatosis, has been reported in a very small number of cases [2]. One such case is presented below.

Case report

A 62-year-old woman was presented with slowly progressive abdominal distension, for the past 5 years. There was no family history of constitutional, dietary or alcohol abuse. Lipogram revealed a total cholesterol

level of 208 mg/dl and serum triglycerides of 304 mg/dl. Severe abdominal distension, noted on physical examination, was confirmed by ultrasound and computed tomography, which excluded ascites, hepatomegaly and hepatic steatosis. Imaging, the patient presented a diffuse fatty infiltration of the abdomen, including the peritoneum and retroperitoneal space, with slight compression of the intestinal loops and anterior displacement of the kidneys; fine fibers with slightly higher density were present in the fatty mass (fig.1).

With the diagnosis of diffuse infiltrative abdominal lipomatosis, surgical intervention was performed for excisional and biopsy purposes. Approximately 15 kg of fatty mass was surgically resected, with the histopathological examination finding adipose tissue without nuclear atypia. The surgical outcome was simple, with discharge after 10 days, with no recurrence recorded at 5 years.

Fig. 1

Discussions

Lipomatous tumors are the most common tumors with mesenchymal origin of the abdominal cavity. They usually develop in the retroperitoneal space, but can also occur in the peritoneal cavity. Lipomatous tumors can be benign or malignant, their histological character having prognostic and therapeutic significance. Simple benign lipomas are encapsulated tumors, with a structure similar to that of normal adipose tissue. Diffuse infiltrative lipomatosis is histologically benign, but has an invasive evolutionary tendency.

Malignant lipomatous tumors (liposarcomas) are usually inhomogeneous, poorly demarcated and invasive [1].

Diffuse infiltrative lipomatosis can have various anatomical locations.

Symmetrical multiple lipomatosis (benign symmetric lipomatosis, Madelung's disease, Launois-Bensaude syndrome,) is a rare entity, affecting mainly men aged 25-60 years. It is characterized by the conglomeration of multiple non-encapsulated lipomas, located symmetrically in the subcutaneous tissues of the

cervical, thoracic, abdominal and pelvic regions. The lesion probably originates in the hypodermis, subsequently penetrating the fascia and muscle structures and invading intervisceral space [3]. Benign symmetrical abdominal lipomatosis is a subtype of multiple symmetrical lipomatosis characterized by massive enlargement of the abdomen (pseudoascites), due to the accumulation of intra- and retroperitoneal fat. Although it has been described in association with alcohol abuse, metabolic abnormalities, polyneuropathy and certain malignant tumors, its etiopathogenesis remains unclear [3].

Computed tomography is recognized as an accurate and clinically useful method for the evaluation of mesenchymal tumors of the abdominal cavity. The CT appearance of abdominal lipomatous tumors correlates closely with the macro- and microscopic anatomical aspects [1]. All lipomas, diffuse lipomatous infiltrates, and liposarcomas have the same fat density histologically and imagingly. Simple benign lipomas are well-demarcated, noninvasive, and encapsulated tumors; diffuse infiltrative lipomatosis masses are large, invasive, and non-encapsulated, permeated by fine, denser fibers, grow along fascial planes, and may infiltrate muscle. Liposarcomas are usually inhomogeneous, poorly demarcated, and invasive, and have higher Hounsfield CT units than normal body fat [1,5].

A positive diagnosis of diffuse infiltrative lipomatosis is established by histological examination, as a number of other conditions may have a similar clinical presentation.

On histological examination, diffuse infiltrative lipomatosis is distinguished from lipoblastomatosis by the absence of lobules and fetal/embryonic adipose tissue and from liposarcoma by the absence of lipoblastic proliferation, pleomorphism, and mitoses [1,6]. There is no evidence that diffuse infiltrative lipomatosis can become malignant.

Surgical treatment is the only therapeutic option and aims to surgically remove the adipose tissue that is causing visceral compression or for cosmetic reasons.

Complete surgical resection is almost never possible, and postoperative recurrence is common [3,4].

Conclusions

Diffuse infiltrative abdominal lipomatosis, involving the abdominal cavity, including the retroperitoneal spaces, is a rare condition. Computed tomography allows determination of the location, size and extent of the lipomatous mass, as well as its relationship to neighboring anatomical structures, being useful both for diagnosis, as well as for planning a surgical approach and in assessing the feasibility of complete resection.

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